

THE ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AS A MEDIATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP AND WORK ENVIRONMENT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

¹Mohammad Hidayatulloh, ²Sri Wahyu Lely hana Setyanti, ³Markus Apriono

¹Postgraduate Student, ^{2,3}Postgraduate Lecturer
Faculty of Economics and Business
University of Jember, Jember, Indonesia

Abstract- Dinas Bina Marga, Sumber Daya Air Dan Bina Konstruksi Kabupaten Bondowoso is a Regional Apparatus Organization formed by the Bondowoso Regency Regional Government with the main duties and functions as the implementing agency for government affairs in the field of public works and spatial planning. The leadership of a Head of Service in each regional apparatus organization under the Bondowoso Regency Government is determined by rotation, where the turnover is very fast. Employees are required to be able to demonstrate good performance, by improving good performance, this can be done by improving performance, creating a supportive work environment and being flexible in accepting the leadership style of each leader which continues to change, so employee commitment and performance continues to be tested. In other words, the performance of employees within the Bondowoso Regency Government is less than optimal. The sample consisted of 99 State Civil Service employees, using method Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) dan Partial Least Square (PLS). Based on this, researchers are interested in examining Transformational Leadership and the Work Environment's influence in improving employee performance with Organizational Commitment as mediation.

Keyword: Transformational Leadership, Work Environment, employee performance, Organizational Commitment.

INTRODUCTION

Dinas Bina Marga, Sumber Daya Air Dan Bina Konstruksi Kabupaten Bondowoso is a Regional Apparatus Organization formed by the Bondowoso Regency Regional Government with the main duties and functions as the implementing agency for government affairs in the field of public works and spatial planning. With responsibility for formulating development policies, implementing minimum service standards and public service standards as well as implementing community satisfaction index measurement facilities and implementing coaching, supervision, performance and behavior assessments for subordinates in accordance with provisions for increasing discipline, motivation, work performance and career development in the development sector clans, water resources and construction development.

The existing phenomenon is a Service Head can be placed there for a minimum period of 2 years to 5 years, so that the leadership of a service head is very flexible, this of course has the possibility of affecting the psychology and psychology of each subordinate. Employees believe that the work environment influences them in carrying out their assigned tasks. Starting from the physical work environment, namely the physical conditions found around the workplace directly or indirectly. To improve good performance, this can be done by improving performance and creating a work environment that is supportive and flexible in accepting the changing leadership style of each leader so that employee commitment and performance continues to be tested.

Another phenomenon, namely, regarding the assessment of the performance status of regional government administration held by the Ministry of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia in 2022, places Bondowoso Regency with the BB predicate, which means it gets a score in the range of 70-80 with the illustration that the Performance Accountability Report (LAKIP) is very both in 2/3 of the work units, both the main work units and supporting work units. In other words, the performance of employees within the Bondowoso Regency Government is less than optimal.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Transformational Leadership

This leadership style refers to efforts to make changes that will increase organizational effectiveness and employee performance, by changing personal values within oneself. Transformational leadership is one of the many leadership styles that exist, because basically this leadership style is applied by many people who become superiors/leaders and it is carried out by every human being unconsciously. Transformational leadership is leadership that stimulates and inspires followers to make changes beyond their personal interests, so as to improve individual performance and organizational effectiveness (Al-husseini & Elbeltagib, 2018). Transformational leadership is often defined by its impact on how leaders strengthen attitudes of mutual cooperation and trust, collective self-advancement, and team learning. Transformational leadership further increases follower motivation and performance (Viprastha, 2018). Transformational leadership in its definition is its impact on how leaders strengthen attitudes of

mutual cooperation and trust, collective self-improvement, and team learning (Muhammad & Rahardja, 2021). Transformational leadership consists of 4 main dimensions, Idealized Influence, Inspiration Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, Individual Consideration.

Work Environment

The work environment is an important factor in creating employee performance. Because the work environment has a direct influence on employees in completing work which will ultimately improve organizational performance. The work environment in a company means a place to interact. This means the condition of a place related to work activities, for example co-workers, leaders, work equipment and work space. Of course, all of these things affect the emotional state of employees (Nguyen, et, al., 2020). The work environment is also an important factor that influences employee performance (Kale and Mazaheri, 2014).

Work is not only a physical matter, but also involves emotional states, by building a healthy, comfortable and harmonious work environment, it will significantly affect work morale, thereby increasing work productivity (Idris, et, al., 2020). The indicators of the physical work environment are lighting/light in the work room, temperature/air temperature in the work room, humidity in the work room, air circulation in the work room, noise in the work room, unpleasant odors in the work room, color scheme in the work room.

Employee Performance

Performance is a sign of the success or failure of a person or group in carrying out real work that has been determined by an organization. Performance in its function does not stand alone but is related to individual, organizational and external environmental factors (Jufrizen, 2018). Performance can be interpreted as the results of work achieved by someone during a certain period of time. Employee performance is a measure that can be used to determine comparisons of the results of carrying out tasks, responsibilities given by the organization in a certain period and can relatively be used to measure work performance (Siagian & Khair, 2018). Performance is a communication process that is carried out continuously in partnership between employees and their direct superiors (Wibowo, 2016). Ardiansyah and Surjanti (2020) and Rahman and Kistyanto (2019) stated that there are five performance indicators, Quality of Work, Quantity of Work, Timeliness, Cooperation, Attitude.

Organizational Commitment

Employees with organizational commitment impose a sense of obligation on employees to give back what the organization has provided (Kurniawan, 2015). Employee motivation is very effective in increasing organizational commitment and employee performance where these motivational factors are measured through intrinsic factors (need for achievement and importance) and extrinsic factors (job security, salary and promotion). Employees' organizational commitment to continue working as part of an organization will increase if it is supported by high motivation from employees related to their work (Lutfi, 2018). Commitment in an organization is seen as a driving force for employees to work hard to achieve predetermined work goals (Adhan et al, 2019). Indicators of Organizational Commitment are, Loyalty, Sticking to the Rules, Attachment to the Organization, Involvement in the Organization, Responsibility, Availability to the Organization.

Research Conceptual Framework

Based on the theoretical review and previous research, it is explained that performance or job performance is defined as a person's success in carrying out work, or successful role achievement that a person obtains from his actions. The conceptual framework in this study aims to analyze which variables are positioned as exogenous variables of transformational leadership (X1) and work environment (X2). The intervening organizational commitment variable (Z) and the endogenous variable of employee performance (Y). The research conceptual framework is shown as follow in figure 1:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Research Hypothesis Development

1. Transformational Leadership on Organizational Commitment

Transformational leadership relates to the process of how certain leaders can inspire their followers to achieve more than is usually expected of them by stimulating higher level needs (Tamengkel and Rumawas, 2022). The research results of Widodo and Mawarto (2020) and Eliyana and Muzaki (2019) show that Transformational Leadership has a positive and significant effect on

Organizational Commitment. At Dinas Bina Marga, Sumber Daya Air Dan Bina Konstruksi Kabupaten Bondowoso, the position of the head of the department often changes according to regional government decisions. Therefore the hypothesis developed is:

H1 : Transformational Leadership has a significant effect on Organizational Commitment.

2. Work Environment on Organizational Commitment

The environment within the company means the place of interaction is the condition of a place related to work activities, for example colleagues, leaders, work equipment and work space. Of course, all of these things affect the emotional state of employees (Nguyen, et, al., 2020). The research results of Ahakwa, Yang, Tackie and Atingabili (2021) and Cahyani and Prianthara (2022) show that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. Therefore the hypothesis developed is:

H2 : Work environment has a significant effect on organizational commitment.

3. Transformational Leadership on Performance

Transformational leadership further increases follower motivation and performance (Viprastha, 2018). With this transformational leadership style, followers feel trust, admiration, loyalty and respect for the leader and followers are motivated to do more than expected. The research results of Widodo and Mawarto (2020) and Sugiarti (2022) show that Transformational Leadership has a positive and significant effect on Performance. Therefore the hypothesis developed is:

H3 : Transformational Leadership has a significant effect on Performance

4. Work Environment on Performance

Good working environment conditions will make employees feel comfortable at work and will have an impact on improving employee performance. Discomfort from the work environment experienced by employees can have fatal consequences, namely decreased performance (Susilaningsih, 2013: 6). The research results of Lopez-Cabarcos, Vazquez-Rodríguez and Quinoa-Pineiro (2022) and Bakker, Hetland, Olsen and Espevik (2022) show that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on performance. Therefore the hypothesis developed is:

H4 : Work environment has a significant effect on performance

5. Organizational Commitment to Performance

Employees' organizational commitment to continue working as part of an organization will increase if it is supported by high motivation from employees related to their work (Lutfi, 2018). The research results of Ahakwa, Yang, Tackie and Atingabili (2021) and Cahyani and Prianthara (2022) show that Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Performance. Therefore the hypothesis developed is:

H5 : Organizational Commitment has a significant effect on Performance

6. Transformational Leadership on Performance through Organizational Commitment

The research results of Satyanegara, Supriyantoro and Pamungkas (2023) and Ragil and Riyanti (2023) found that Transformational Leadership has an effect on Performance which is mediated by Organizational Commitment. This shows that Transformational Leadership applied by an organizational leader is transformational leadership which is related to the process of how leaders can inspire their followers to achieve targets beyond what is usually expected by stimulating higher level needs (Tamengkel and Rumawas, 2022). Therefore the hypothesis developed is:

H6 : Transformational Leadership has a significant effect on Performance through Organizational Commitment

7. Work Environment on Performance through Organizational Commitment

The research results of Ahakwa, Yang, Tackie and Atingabili (2021) and Cahyani and Prianthara (2022) found that the work environment has an effect on performance which is mediated by organizational commitment. This shows that creating a conducive work environment has an impact on increasing work productivity (Idris, et, al., 2020). Therefore the hypothesis developed is:

H7 : Work environment has a significant effect on performance through organizational commitment

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research design

Based on the background and problem formulation, the characteristics of the problem studied in this research are categorized as Explanatory Research, namely research used to show the position of the variables studied and the influence between one variable and another variable (Sugiyono, 2012:21). Hypothesis testing is basically testing the generalization of research results based on a sample (Mufarrikoh, 2019:27). This research was conducted at Dinas Bina Marga, Sumber Daya Air Dan Bina Konstruksi Kabupaten Bondowoso and this research is explanatory research. This research aims to analyze the causal or cause-effect relationship between the independent variables which consist of the Transformational Leadership and Work Environment variables; intervening variable, namely Organizational Commitment; and the dependent variable, namely Employee Performance.

Population and Sample

Population is a complete group of elements, which are usually people, objects, transactions, or events that researchers are interested in studying or making as research objects. Population in another definition means the entire number of subjects that will be studied by a researcher (Kuncoro, 2001; Sugiyono, 2008; Prasetia 2022). In this research, the population is all employees of

the State Civil Apparatus at Dinas Bina Marga, Sumber Daya Air Dan Bina Konstruksi Kabupaten Bondowoso with the following details:

Table 1. List of ASN Fields and Employees at Dinas Bina Marga, Sumber Daya Air Dan Bina Konstruksi Kabupaten Bondowoso

Field	Number Of Employees
Sekretariat	23
Bina Marga	15
Sumber Daya Air	12
Bina Konstruksi	9
Operasi Dan Pemeliharaan	20
Unit Pelaksana Teknis Dinas	20
Amount	99

Source : Dinas BSBK Personnel Data for 2023.

The sample was taken using a saturated sample/census, namely a technique for determining a sample with all members of the population selected as samples (Sugiyono, 2013: 85). A sample is also a set of observation units that provide information or data needed by a study (Agung, 1992; Amirullah, 2022). This research will use a non-probability sampling method, where the sampling technique does not provide equal opportunities or opportunities for each element or member of the population to be selected as a sample. The sampling technique will use a saturated sample technique, namely using all members of the population (99 people).

Types and Sources of Data

The data used in this research is quantitative data, namely a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, which is used to research certain populations or samples, where data collection uses research instruments, and data analysis is quantitative, and has the aim of testing hypotheses that have been determined (Sugiyono, 2012:8). In this research, the data used comes from internal data from within regional apparatus organizations which describes the current situation at Dinas Bina Marga, Sumber Daya Air Dan Bina Konstruksi Kabupaten Bondowoso.

In this study, the data sources came from 2 (two) data sources, namely:

1. Primary data

Primary data is data obtained directly through field research which is personal responses from respondents. In this research, the primary data taken relates to the identity of the respondent, the opinion of the respondent while working as Dinas Bina Marga, Sumber Daya Air Dan Bina Konstruksi Kabupaten Bondowoso.

2. Secondary Data

Secondary data is regular objective data provided by a second party or processed by a third party in the form of brochures, reports and other data.

Data Collection Methods

In this research, the method for collecting data uses a questionnaire. The type of questionnaire distributed is a closed questionnaire and the measurements are prepared using a Likert scale, namely by measuring attitudes where the subject is asked to identify the level of agreement or disagreement with each question, where each question uses a score with alternative choices of 1 to 5.

Methods of Data Analysis

To answer hypothesis testing in this research, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis was used with Smart PLS (Partial Least Square) software. SEM is a multivariate analysis technique that makes it possible to analyze a series of relationships between variables in research simultaneously, which will provide statistical efficiency. SEM analysis makes it possible to test several variables in this research, where the dependent variable or independent and intervening variables will form a model that will be built in this research through literature review and then analyzing the model using SEM.

Smart PLS itself is an SEM analysis method that uses the Variance Based Structural Equation Modeling approach. This approach uses an approach that uses variance in the iteration process so that it does not require correlation between indicators. PLS can be used to predict and analyze (determinant factors) by measuring the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. To get estimates, PLS uses three stages where each stage produces an estimate. The first stage produces a weight estimate, the second stage produces estimates of the inner model and outer model, and the third stage produces estimates of means and location.

Instrument Test

The instrument test in a study aims to determine the quality of the data used, where the instrument test carried out is useful for determining whether the data used can represent the condition of something that is measured from the research subject.

1. Validity test

According to Arikunto (2010:144) Validity test is a measure that shows the level of validity or validity of an instrument. Research results are valid if there are similarities between the data collected and the data that actually occurs on the object under study.

2. Reliability Test

According to Sugiyono (2017: 130), states that a reliability test is the extent to which measurement results using the same object will produce the same data. This reliability test is carried out on respondents using questions that have been declared valid in the validity test and their reliability will be determined. This research uses the alpha method in the Cronbach's Alpha model, where an instrument is said to be reliable if the alpha value is greater than 0.60.

3. Data Normality Test

The data normality test is carried out to find out whether the data obtained is normally distributed or not. The normality test carried out on the sample was carried out using the Kolmogrov-Smirnov test by setting the degree of confidence (α) at 5%. This test is carried out on variables with the condition that individually each variable can also be declared to meet the assumption of normality.

Classic Assumption Test

The classical assumption test is an analysis carried out to assess whether in a linear regression model using least squares calculations or what is called Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) there are classical assumption problems. The classical assumptions themselves are conditions that must be met in the OLS linear regression model so that the model is valid as an estimation tool.

1. Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test is a test of the related assumption that the independent variables in a model are not correlated with each other. One way to see the occurrence of multicollinearity is to look at the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value provided that if the VIF value is < 5 and the Tolerance value is > 0.05 , then it can be stated that there is no multicollinearity.

2. Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in a regression model there is inequality in the variance of the residuals from one observation to another. One test model is the Glacier test to test whether or not there is heteroscedasticity in a regression model. The Glacier Test is carried out by regressing the residual absolute value against all independent variables. If the significant value is more than 0.05 or 5%, then heteroscedasticity does not occur. Symptoms of heteroscedasticity can be seen through the presence or absence of certain patterns on the graph, where the X axis is Y which has been predicted, and the X axis is the residual ($Y_{\text{predicted}} - Y_{\text{actual}}$) which has been unstandardized.

The T Test

The t test is used to test the significance of the influence of each independent variable (X) partially/individually on the dependent variable (Y) with the level of significance used with the following formula:

$$t = \frac{b}{sb}$$

Where:

t = Result of t calculation

b = Regression coefficient of independent variables

sb = Standard error of the regression coefficient can be used with the formula

Data analysis

1. Path Analysis

Path analysis in this research is used to test and analyze the existence of direct and indirect influences between independent and dependent variables. The following can be described as a path analysis model.

Figure 2. Research Path Analysis Model

2. Sobel Testing (Sobel Test)

The Sobel test is a test used to find out whether there is a significant relationship through a mediating variable. Where these variables are tested whether they are able to act as mediators in this relationship. In this relationship, the sobel test method uses an intervening variable as a mediator of the relationship from the independent variable to the dependent variable. This is used to test how big a variable's role is in mediating the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable which is used with the sobel test.

Research Model Using PLS SEM Method (Varian Based)

When testing using the SEM PLS method, it is necessary to develop a research model that explains the relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables which are explained by each indicator as follows:

Figure 3. SEM PLS Testing Model

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

1. Convergent Validity

Measuring the convergent validity of the means model with Reflective indicators can be seen from the correlation between the item/indicator values and the construct value of each indicator. These values are the most important part of the continuation of the analysis and research process because each value determines the research results.

a. Loading Factor

Indicators are considered valid with a correlation value above 0.70, so that at the research stage of development of the loading scale, 0.50 to 0.60 is acceptable (Ghozali, 35:2021). So the researchers used the middle value of the theory, namely 0.60. The following are the results of the loading factor analysis in this research:

Table 2. Loading Factor Test Results

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	Rule Of Thumb	Result
KT1	X1.1	0,951	0,600	valid
KT2	X1.2	0,931	0,600	valid
KT3	X1.3	0,896	0,600	valid
KT4	X1.4	0,942	0,600	valid
LK1	X2.1	0,848	0,600	valid
LK2	X2.2	0,926	0,600	valid
LK3	X2.3	0,862	0,600	valid
LK4	X2.4	0,808	0,600	valid
LK5	X2.5	0,738	0,600	valid
KP1	Y1.1	0,869	0,600	valid
KP2	Y1.2	0,753	0,600	valid
KP3	Y1.3	0,845	0,600	valid
KP4	Y1.4	0,881	0,600	valid
KP5	Y1.5	0,864	0,600	valid
KO1	Z1.1	0,755	0,600	valid
KO2	Z1.2	0,907	0,600	valid
KO3	Z1.3	0,906	0,600	valid
KO4	Z1.4	0,908	0,600	valid
KO5	Z1.5	0,890	0,600	valid
KO6	Z1.5	0,886	0,600	valid

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

b. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

The indicator validity process using extracted variant average is carried out by comparing the extracted variant average value, this value is used to measure the accuracy of each indicator for each variable. With the results, the average value of a good extracted variant is greater than 0.50 (Ghozali, 68:2021)

Table 3. Varage Variant Extracted (AVE) Test Results

Variable	AVE	Rule Of Thumb	Result
Transformational Leadership	0,865	0,500	Valid
Work Environment	0,712	0,500	Valid
Performance	0,769	0,500	Valid
Organizational Commitment	0,703	0,500	Valid

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

2. Discriminate Validity

In carrying out measurements in a study, Discriminate Validity is the initial requirement for analyzing the relationship between latent variables through former larker. The Forner Larker value can be achieved if the top value of each column is greater than the column below.

Table 4. Forner Larker Discriminate Validity Test Results

Variable	Transformational Leadership	Performance	Organizational Commitment	Work Environment	Result
Transformational Leadership	0,930				Achieved
Performance	0,225	0,844			Achieved
Organizational Commitment	0,676	0,157	0,877		Achieved
Work Environment	0,412	0,557	0,557	0,839	Achieved

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

3. Reliability

In the research measurement model (outer model), apart from validity testing, reliability testing is also needed which aims to prove the accuracy, consistency and correctness of the instrument in measuring the construct.

a. Cronbach's Alpha (CA)

Cronbach alpha is used to measure the reliability value of a variable which is considered reliable if the value is > 0.70 (Ghozali, 41:2014). The Cronbach alpha scale is grouped into 5, namely; scale 0.00 - 0.20 (very unreliable), scale 0.21 - 0.41 (not reliable), scale 0.42 - 0.60 (fairly reliable), scale 0.61 - 0.80 (reliable) and a scale of 0.81 - 1.00 (very reliable).

Table 5. Cronbach Alpha Reliability Test Results

Variable	CA	Rule Thumb	Of Category
Transformational Leadership	0,948	0,700	Reliabel
Work Environment	0,894	0,700	Reliabel
Performance	0,899	0,700	Reliabel
Organizational Commitment	0,939	0,700	Reliabel

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

b. Composite Reliability

Next, the reliability test uses composite reliability, the reliability measurement results are declared reliable if the value of composite reliability is > 0.70 .

Table 6. Cronbach Alpha Reliability Test Results

Variable	CR	Rule Thumb	Of Kategori
Transformational Leadership	0,962	0,700	Reliabel
Work Environment	0,922	0,700	Reliabel
Performance	0,925	0,700	Reliabel
Organizational Commitment	0,952	0,700	Reliabel

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Inner Model Analysis

After the outer model testing is carried out with satisfactory results, it is continued with testing the structural model (inner model). This test consists of the R-Square test with the aim of determining the magnitude of the influence of the independent variables and path coefficient testing to measure the magnitude of the influence of each variable.

Figure 4. SmartPLS 3.0 Partial Least Square Testing Model

Path Efficiency

Path coefficient testing is hypothesis testing, whether or not a hypothesis is accepted can be determined through path coefficient testing. This test uses the booth strapping method in SmartPLS 3.0. This test was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of each variable. There are 2 types of path coefficient testing, namely direct influence and indirect influence. Hypothesis testing in this research can be accepted if the resulting P-values are <0.05 to determine the direction of the relationship between variables determined by the original sample values.

1. Direct Influence

Table 7. Direct Influence Path Coefficient Test Results

Variable	Original (O)	Sample	P-Value	Result
Transformational Leadership -> Organizational Commitment	0,689		0,000	Significant
Work Environment -> Organizational Commitment	- 0,030		0,742	Not Significant
Transformational Leadership -> Performance	- 0,030		0,789	Not Significant
Work Environment -> Performance	0,561		0,000	Significant
Organizational Commitment -> Performance	0,036		0,770	Not Significant

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Based on the direct influence test in table 7, it can be seen that:

- a. The first hypothesis (H1), the original sample value of transformational leadership (X1) on organizational commitment (Z) is $\beta = 0.689$ which shows a positive direction or in the same direction, while the p-values are $0.000 < 0.050$ or show significant results. Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis is accepted so that transformational leadership (X1) is proven to have an effect on organizational commitment (Z).
- b. The second hypothesis (H2), the original sample value of the work environment (X2) on organizational commitment (Z) is $\beta = - 0.030$ which shows a negative direction or the opposite direction, while the p-values are $0.742 > 0.050$ or show no results. significant. Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis is rejected so that the work environment (X2) is proven to have no effect on organizational commitment (Z).
- c. The third hypothesis (H3), the original sample value of transformational leadership (X1) on performance (Y) is $\beta = - 0.030$ which shows a negative or opposite direction, while the p-values are $0.789 > 0.050$ or show insignificant results . Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis is rejected so that transformational leadership (X1) is proven to have no effect on performance (Y).
- d. The fourth hypothesis (H4), the original sample value of the work environment (X2) on performance (Y) is $\beta = 0.561$ which shows a positive direction or in the same direction, while the p-values are $0.000 < 0.050$ or show significant results. Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis is accepted so that the work environment (X2) is proven to have an effect on performance (Y).

e. The fifth hypothesis (H2), the original sample value of organizational commitment (Z) on performance (Y) is $\beta = 0.036$ which indicates a positive direction or in the same direction, while the p-values are $0.770 > 0.050$ or show insignificant results. Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis is rejected so that organizational commitment (Z) is proven to have no effect on performance (Y).

2. Indirect Influence

Table 8. Direct Influence Path Coefficient Test Results

Variable	Original Sample (O)	P-Value	Result
Transformational Leadership -> Organizational Commitment	0,025	0,774	Not Significant
Work Environment -> Organizational Commitment	- 0,001	0,929	Not Significant

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Based on the direct influence test in table 8, it can be seen that:

a. The sixth hypothesis (H6), the original sample value of transformational leadership (X1) through organizational commitment (Z) on performance (Y) is $\beta = 0.025$ which indicates a positive or unidirectional direction, while the p-values are $0.774 > 0.050$ or showed insignificant results. Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that the sixth hypothesis is rejected so that organizational commitment (Z) cannot mediate the relationship between transformational leadership (X1) and performance (Y).

b. The seventh hypothesis (H7), the original sample value of the work environment (X2) through organizational commitment (Z) on performance (Y) is $\beta = - 0.001$ which shows a negative or opposite direction, while the p-values are $0.929 > 0.050$ or shows insignificant results. Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that the seventh hypothesis is rejected so that organizational commitment (Z) cannot mediate the relationship between work environment (X2) and performance (Y).

Sobel test

Testing using the Sobel test is used to determine whether the mediating variable is significantly capable of mediating the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The test is carried out by testing the strength of the indirect influence of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable through the mediating variable. With the results of the sobel test calculation as follows:

$$Sab = \sqrt{b^2S + a^D S b^2 + S a^2 S b^2}$$

$$X1 = \frac{\frac{sb}{0,689 \times 0.036}}{0,10} = \frac{0,025}{0,10} = 0,248$$

$$X2 = \frac{\frac{sb}{-0,030 \times 0.036}}{0,10} = \frac{-0,001}{0,10} = -0,011$$

Based on the results of the Sobel test calculation, it shows that the z value (X1) is 0.248 and the z value (X2) is $- 0.011 < 1.96$ (absolute z value) thus proving that the organizational commitment variable (Z) cannot mediate the relationship between the influence of transformational leadership (X1) and work environment (X2) on performance (Y).

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Transformational Leadership on Organizational Commitment

Hypothesis test results show that transformational leadership has a significant effect on organizational commitment with a resulting P-Value of 0.000 or < 0.05 . This shows that the leader applies transformational leadership with indicators of charisma, inspiration, intellectual stimulation and attention to employees, which has been implemented by the head of service in his leadership. Where this condition is supported by the head of the Bondowoso Regency Highways, Water Resources and Construction Department having direct contact with employees, direct interaction during the weekly roll call, the head of the department also holds a monthly coffee agenda together with all employees, as a tool to strengthen department cohesiveness. So that employees feel more committed to the service by seeing the head of the service with transformational leadership.

Apart from transformational leadership with charisma or authority, service heads are also inspirational leaders and transformational leadership through problem solving. The head of department also holds regular weekly meetings on the progress of implementation and evaluation of activities with heads of divisions, heads of sub-divisions/sub-coordinators, heads of UPTD. Where department heads provide opportunities for office holders to complete their respective activities according to their functional duties, this makes employees more confident and committed to the organization/department.

The results of this research support research conducted by Anis Eliyana, Syamsul Ma'arif, Muzakki (2019), that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment, this is because middle-level leaders at PT. Pelabuhan Indonesia III applies transformational leadership to make employees under it have a higher commitment to the company.

The Effect of Work Environment on Organizational Commitment

The results of the hypothesis test show that the work environment has no significant effect on organizational commitment with the resulting P-Value value being 0.742 or > 0.05 . This shows that the work environment available for employees to work with indicators of the availability of work room lighting, work room humidity, work room noise conditions, work room air circulation and work room color scheme in the District Highways, Water Resources and Construction Development Department Bondowoso has no effect on employee commitment to the organization/department. This condition is based on the stigma among employees that large departments have better facilities than smaller departments, so it is a natural assumption that the work environment in the civil development, water resources and construction services departments is good and does not affect organizational commitment.

Strong organizational commitment is not only purely a feeling of comfort and appropriateness of the employee's working environment at work, but there are several other factors that influence employee commitment such as compensation (salary, benefits, incentives and others). The results of this research support research conducted by Intan Purnama, Nyoto and Asmara Hendra Komara (2019), that a good work environment can actually reduce employee organizational commitment at Pelita Indonesia College Pekanbaru. It was concluded that whether or not the work environment at the College was good Pelita Indonesia Pekanbaru did not have an impact on increasing or decreasing employee organizational commitment.

The Effect of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance

The results of the hypothesis test show that transformational leadership has no significant effect on employee performance with the resulting P-Value value being $0.789 > 0.050$ or showing insignificant results. Transformational leadership which is implemented better does not completely affect the performance of employees of the Bondowoso Regency Highways, Water Resources and Construction Development Department, this is because employees are already accustomed to changing service heads by applying a transformational leadership style. Another factor in the lack of influence of transformational leadership on employee performance is that employees' thinking is not focused on who the leader/department head is in charge, because employees are already focused on the main tasks and functions of their position.

Apart from that, employees also receive less appreciation from department heads, giving rewards and punishments is needed by employees. Where each employee is required to carry out their respective main tasks and functions within a specified completion time, this creates a burden for employees. By carrying out tasks according to the specified targets, it will be an achievement for the department, conversely, if there is a delay in completing work tasks, it will have a direct impact on the employee. This is the basis that transformational leadership does not have a significant effect on employee performance, where every few years a change in department heads does not affect employee performance much, this happens because employees are used to changes or changes in leadership.

The results of this research support research conducted by Amy Nurchuda, Sigit Sardjono, Wulan Purnamasari (2019), stating that leadership style has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance. To improve a good leadership style, this is done by encouraging employees so that employee performance is better for Anwar Medika Sidoarjo Hospital employees.

The Effect of Work Environment on Employee Performance

The results of the hypothesis test show that the work environment has a significant effect on employee performance with a P-Value value of 0.000 or < 0.05 . So that the better the working environment conditions, the better the employee's performance will be, if the workplace facilities are comfortable and good, it will make employees more enthusiastic about working. On the other hand, poor working environment conditions result in a decrease in employee performance.

The condition of the work environment with lighting conditions in the work room, humidity in the work room, noise conditions in the work room, air circulation in the work room and color scheme in the work room at the Bondowoso Regency Highways, Water Resources and Construction Development Department is in good condition with adequate facilities for employees. Apart from the work environment indicators above, employees are also provided with good work equipment such as office furniture, WiFi network, line network, computer equipment, computer equipment (printers, scanners, projectors) which support employees in carrying out their work. This makes employees feel comfortable at work so that employee performance increases. Sometimes employees are required to work overtime because of time demands/time limits that have been targeted. This good working environment conditions keep employees in a good mood and not stressed even though they have to work overtime until midnight.

The results of this research support research conducted by Doni Irawan, Gatot Kusjono, Suprianto (2021), with the research results that the work environment has a significant effect on employee performance, this means that the work environment at the Serpong sub-district office has a great influence on the performance of civil servants when working .

The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance

The results of the hypothesis test show that organizational commitment has no significant effect on employee performance with the resulting P-Value value being $0.770 > 0.050$ or showing insignificant results. Organizational commitment with indicators of loyalty, adhering to rules, attachment, involvement and responsibility does not have a significant effect on the performance of employees of the Bondowoso Regency Highways, Water Resources and Construction Development Department, this occurs because of the commitment of employees with State Civil Apparatus status who are ready to be placed anywhere. It just makes employees feel that even when their performance declines it will not affect their employment status and they are ready if they have to be transferred to another service.

Meanwhile, performance indicators include quality of work with accuracy and accountability, quantity of work carried out competently, punctuality of work in accordance with the predetermined time period, ability to collaborate with colleagues and direct superiors, work attitude in accordance with ASN's core values, namely being oriented. service, accountability, competence, harmony, loyalty, adaptability, and collaboration are not really influenced by the organizational commitment of each employee. In principle, if employees have a high commitment to the organization, they will consciously carry out their performance to the maximum with a commitment to an organization that can be trusted, but the conditions that occur show that the performance of employees remains optimal regardless of where the State Civil Service employees are placed. The results of this research support research conducted by Agus Purwanto, John Tampil Purba, Innocentius Bernarto, Rosdiana Sianggaran (2021), organizational commitment has no significant effect on performance variables, meaning that organizational commitment has no effect on the performance of senior employees and managers of family business companies in Banten .

The Effect of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment

The results of the hypothesis test show that transformational leadership does not have a significant effect on employee performance through organizational commitment with the resulting P-Value value being $0.774 > 0.050$ or showing insignificant results, where organizational commitment cannot mediate transformational leadership on performance. The direct relationship between transformational leadership and performance has an insignificant effect, the same as the indirect relationship which has an insignificant effect. This means that department heads with transformational leadership cannot influence the performance of Bondowoso Regency Highways, Water Resources and Construction Development Department employees, even though the employees have a commitment to the department. So organizational commitment is not the main factor in improving employee performance.

As a department head, using a transformational leadership style is a good managerial method for employees so that their performance is stable and even improved. Employee performance will continue to be carried out in accordance with the main duties and functions of each position held by the employees, with the commitment of each employee's personality. There is no or no mediation (no mediation effect) of organizational commitment from the influence of transformational leadership and employee performance. The results of this research support research conducted by Iskandar, Faisal Matriadi, Aiyub (2019), where organizational commitment does not mediate the influence of transformational leadership on the performance of Polri personnel at Lhokseumawe Police. This shows that organizational commitment is not a mediator in the relationship between transformational leadership and the performance of Polri personnel.

The Effect of Work Environment on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment

The results of the hypothesis test show that the work environment has no significant effect on employee performance through organizational commitment with the resulting P-Value value being $0.929 > 0.050$ or showing insignificant results, where organizational commitment cannot mediate the work environment on performance. The direct relationship between the work environment and performance has a significant influence, but the indirect relationship has an insignificant influence. This means that employee performance will be maximized if there is a work environment with good facilities. Commitment to the service of each employee cannot mediate the conditions of the work environment with employee performance.

This means that the existence of organizational commitment to each employee does not change employee performance, supported by adequate work environment facilities. With good working conditions at the Bondowoso Regency Highways, Water Resources and Construction Services Department, employees can improve their performance comfortably and according to targets. So the results of this research are different and do not support research conducted by Rizqul Anis, I Made Bayu Dirgantara, Meirani Harsasi (2022), where organizational commitment is a variable that mediates the influence of the work environment on the performance of police officers in the Pekalongan Police traffic unit.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion that the researcher has explained, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Transformational leadership has a significant effect on organizational commitment. The results of this research show that the first hypothesis (H1) is accepted.
2. The work environment has no significant effect on organizational commitment, the results of this research indicate that the second hypothesis (H2) is rejected.
3. Transformational leadership has no significant effect on employee performance. The results of this research indicate that the third hypothesis (H3) is rejected.
4. The work environment has a significant effect on employee performance. The results of this research indicate that the fourth hypothesis (H4) is accepted.
5. Organizational commitment does not have a significant effect on employee performance. The results of this research indicate that the fifth hypothesis (H5) is rejected.

6. Organizational commitment cannot mediate the effect of transformational leadership on employee performance. The results of this study indicate that the sixth hypothesis (H6) is rejected.
7. Organizational commitment cannot mediate the influence of the work environment on employee performance. The results of this study indicate that the seventh hypothesis (H7) is rejected.

REFERENCES:

1. Dubrin Andrew J. 2015. Leadership (Terjemahan), Edisi Kedua. Jakarta: Prenada Media.
2. Gary, Yulk. 2012. Leadership in Organization. Prentice-Hall. Inc.
3. Ghozali, Imam. 2013. Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program SPSS. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
4. Kadarisman, M. 2012. Manajemen Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
5. Santoso, S. 2012. Latihan SPSS Statistik Parametrik. Jakarta: PT. Elex Media Komputindo.
6. Sugiyono. 2013. Metode Penelitian Pendidikan Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D. Bandung: Alfabeta.
7. Syahrir, et al. 2020. Aplikasi SEM-PLS dalam Pengelolaan Sumber Daya Pesisir dan Lautan. Bogor: IPB Press.
8. Fathorrahman. 2023. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Malang: Literasi Nusantara Abadi Grup.
9. Halim. 2020. Sistem Merit dalam Perspektif Perbandingan Hukum Kepegawaian Aparatur Sipil Negara. Yogyakarta: Deepublish.
10. Kaswan. 2019. Perubahan dan Pengembangan Organisasi. Bandung: Yrama Widya.
11. Mambrasar, R., et al. 2021. Effect of Work Environment, Reward, Punishment and Work Discipline on Organizational Commitment (Study on Employees of the Regional Financial Management Agency of Tambrau Regency, West Papua Province). International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development, 3(6), 48-59.
12. Maulidiyah, N.N dkk. 2022. Perilaku Organisasi. Padang: Global Eksekutif Teknologi.
13. Niar, H., dkk. 2022. Dasar-Dasar Manajemen. Bandung: Media Sains Indonesia.
14. Nimran & Amirullah. 2022. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia & Perilaku Organisasi. Malang: Media Nusa Creative.
15. Prasetya, I. 2022. Metodologi Penelitian Pendekatan Teori dan Praktik. Medan: UMSU Press.
16. Rezeki, dkk. 2021. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia dalam Organisasi. Bandung: Media Sains Indonesia.
17. Setyadi, D. 2019. Pengaruh Learning Organization dan Kepemimpinan Transformasional terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan PT Trisensa Mineral Utama di Kabupaten Kutai Kartanegara. Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen Mulawarman (JIMM), 4(4).
18. Sinambela, L.P. 2021. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
19. Singarimbun, M. 1999. Metode dan Proses Penelitian dalam Metode Penelitian Survei. Yogyakarta: LP3ES.
20. Wardhana, dkk. 2022. Manajemen Kinerja (Konsep, Teori, dan Penerapannya). Bandung: Media Sains Indonesia.
21. Widiastuti, I. 2022. Kebijakan Publik. Solok: Insan Cendekia Mandiri.
22. Widyatmika. 2020. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional Terhadap Komitmen Organisasional, dengan Kepuasan Kerja sebagai Variabel Mediasi. E-Jurnal Manajemen, Vol. 9, No. 10, 2020 : 3486-3505.
23. Winata, E. 2022. Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia Lingkungan Kerja. Lombok: Pusat Pengembangan Pendidikan dan Penelitian Indonesia.
24. Hartanto, D. A., Ghalib, S., & Irwansyah. 2021. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional, Kepuasan Kerja, Dan Komitmen Organisasional Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. Jurnal Bisnis dan Pembangunan, 10, 37-41.
25. Iskandar, Matriadi, F., & Aiyub. 2019. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional Dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Personil Polri Dengan Komitmen Organisasi Sebagai Variabel Intervening Pada Polres. Jurnal Manajemen Indonesia (J-Mind), 41-66.
26. Juliarti, N. T., & Anindita, R. 2022. Peran Kepemimpinan Karismatik dan Work- Life Balance Terhadap Komitmen Organisasional Melalui Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan pada Industri Broadcasting. Jenius, 5, 298-313.
27. Muhammad, A. R., & Rahardja, E. 2021. Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional Dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Dengan Komitmen Organisasional Sebagai Variabel Intervening. Diponegoro Journal Of Management, 10, 1-12.
28. Novitasari, D., & Asbari, M. 2020. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan: Peran Kesiapan Untuk Berubah Sebagai Mediator. Jurnal Manajemen, 84-99.
29. Pariesti, A., Christa, U. R., & Meitiana. 2022. Pengaruh Kompetensi Dan Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Dengan Motivasi Sebagai Variabel Intervening Pada Kantor Inspektorat Kabupaten Katingan. Journal of Environment an Management, 35-45. doi:https://doi.org/10.37304/jem.v3i1.4284
30. Priyo S., B. 2018. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional, Kompetensi, Dan Motivasi Berprestasi Terhadap Kinerja Konsultan Pengawas Di PT. Eskapindo Matra. Jurnal Revitalisasi Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen, 07, 118-127.
31. Purmawati, E., Suparta, G., & Yasa, S. 2017. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformational dan Pelatihan terhadap Komitmen Organisasi Dan Kinerja Pegawai Pada Dinas Perhubungan Kota Denpasar. Jagadhita: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis., 4(2), 36-54. doi:10.22225/jj.4.2.211.35-54
32. Siswatiningsih, I., Raharjo, K., & Prasetya, A. 2018. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional Dan Transaksional. Jurnal Bisnis dan Manajemen, 146-157.
33. Soelistya, D. 2022. The Importance of the Work Environment as a Mediation on Employee Performance: Affected by Work Life Balance. Budapest International Research and Critics Institute - Journal (BIRCI-Journal), 244-257. doi:https://doi.org/10.33258/birci.v5i1.3599

34. Tahapary, Y., Rahadhini, M. D., & Suprayitno. 2018. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformatif Dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Dengan Komitmen Organisasi Sebagai Variabel Mediasi. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Kewirausahaan*, 294-305.
35. Tamengkel, L., & Rumawas, W. 2022. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformatif Terhadap Kinerja dan Keinginan Keluar Karyawan: Peran Komitmen Organisasional Sebagai Mediator. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis (JAB)*, 12, 52-60.

